

*Article***n-Cyclic Refined Neutrosophic Vector Spaces and Matrices**Malath. F. Aswad ^{1,*}¹ Faculty of science, PhD.of mathematics,GaziAntep University, Turkey; Malaz.aswad@yahoo.com* Correspondence: Malaz.aswad@yahoo.com*Received:* June 2021; *Accepted:* July 2021

Abstract: This paper is dedicated to study for the first time the concept of n-cyclic refined neutrosophic vector space as a direct application of n-cyclic refined neutrosophic sets. Also, It presents some elementary properties of these spaces such as homomorphisms and subspaces. On the other hand, this work defines n-cyclic refined neutrosophic real matrices, and illustrates some examples to clarify these structures.

Keywords: n-cyclic refined neutrosophic vector space, n-cyclic refined neutrosophic ring, n-cyclic refined neutrosophic matrix

1. Introduction

Neutrosophy is a new branch of philosophy which concerns with the indeterminacy in real life actions and sciences. The Neutrosophic is a new view of Modeling , designed to effectively deal underlying doubts in the real world, as it came to replace binary logic that recognized right and wrong by introducing a third neutral case which could be interpreted as non-specific or uncertain. Founded by Florentin Smarandache [6], he presented it in 1999 as a generalization of fuzzy logic. As an extension of this, A. A. Salama introduced the Neutrosophic crisp sets Theory as a generalization of crisp sets theory [53] and developed, inserted and formulated new concepts in the fields of mathematics, statistics, computer science and information systems through neutrosophics [53-56]. In the literature, neutrosophy has got many applications in pure mathematics areas such as space theory [1,2], module theory [4,5], matrix theory [31,32,42], and number theory [3,35]. Also, it plays an important role in applied mathematics such as equations [30], special elements [41], and topology [27,29]. n-cyclic refined neutrosophic sets were defined in [39], and used in the study of some related rings and modules. These sets are considered as a new kind of n-refined neutrosophic sets [12], with a similar structure and different operations. In this work, we define the concept of n-cyclic refined neutrosophic vector spaces and n-cyclic refined neutrosophic matrices. Also, we illustrate many examples to clarify the validity of these concepts, and we list some of related open questions.

2. n-Cyclic Refined neutrosophic vector space.

Definition 2.1 [39]

Let $(R, +, \times)$ be a ring and $I_k; 1 \leq k \leq n$ be n indeterminacies. We define $R_n(I) = \{a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2 + \dots + a_nI_n; a_i \in R\}$ to be n-cyclic refined neutrosophic ring.

Operations on $R_n(I)$ are defined as:

$$\sum_{i=0}^n x_i I_i + \sum_{i=0}^n y_i I_i = \sum_{i=0}^n (x_i + y_i) I_i, \sum_{i=0}^n x_i I_i \times \sum_{i=0}^n y_i I_i = \sum_{i,j=0}^n (x_i \times y_j) I_i I_j = \sum_{i,j=0}^n (x_i \times y_j) I_{(i+j \bmod n)}$$

Where \times is the multiplication on the ring R , and $xI_0 = x$, for all $x \in R$.

Definition 2.2 [39]

Let $(K, +, \times)$ be a field, we say that $K_n(I) = K + KI_1 + \dots + KI_n = \{a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2 + \dots + a_nI_n; a_i \in K\}$ is a n-cyclic refined neutrosophic field.

Definition 2.3

Let $(V, +, \times)$ be any vector space over a field K . Then we say that $V_n(I) = V + VI_1 + \dots + VI_n = \{x_0 + x_1I_1 + \dots + x_nI_n; x_i \in V\}$ is a weak n-cyclic refined neutrosophic vector space over the field K . Elements of $V_n(I)$ are called n-cyclic refined neutrosophic vectors, elements of K are called scalars.

If we take scalars from the n-cyclic refined neutrosophic field $K_n(I)$, we say that $V_n(I)$ is a strong n-cyclic refined neutrosophic vector space over the n-cyclic refined neutrosophic field $K_n(I)$. Elements of $K_n(I)$ are called n-cyclic refined neutrosophic scalars.

Remark 2.1. Multiplication by an n-cyclic refined neutrosophic scalar $m = \sum_{i=0}^n m_i I_i \in K_n(I)$ is defined as:

$$\left(\sum_{i=0}^n m_i I_i\right) \times \left(\sum_{i=0}^n a_i I_i\right) = \sum_{i,j=0}^n (m_i a_j) I_i I_j$$

Where $a_i \in V, m_i \in K, I_i I_j = I_{(i+j \bmod n)}$.

Definition 2.5

Let $V_n(I)$ be a weak n-cyclic refined neutrosophic vector space over the n-cyclic refined neutrosophic field K ; a nonempty $W_n(I)$ is called a weak n-cyclic refined neutrosophic vector subspace of $V_n(I)$ if $W_n(I)$ is a subspace of $V_n(I)$ itself.

Definition 2.6

Let $V_n(I)$ be a strong n-cyclic refined neutrosophic vector space over the n-cyclic refined neutrosophic field $K_n(I)$. A nonempty subset $W_n(I)$ is called a strong n-cyclic refined neutrosophic vector submodule of $V_n(I)$ if $W_n(I)$ is a submodule of $V_n(I)$ itself.

Theorem 2.1

Let $V_n(I)$ be a weak n-cyclic refined neutrosophic vector space over the n-cyclic refined neutrosophic field K , $W_n(I)$ be a nonempty subset of $V_n(I)$. Then $W_n(I)$ is a weak n-cyclic refined neutrosophic subspace if and only if:

$$x + y \in W_n(I), m \times x \in W_n(I) \text{ for all } x, y \in W_n(I), m \in K.$$

proof:

it holds directly from the condition of subspace.

Definition 2.7

Let $V_n(I)$ be a weak n-cyclic refined neutrosophic vector space over the field K , x be an arbitrary element of $V_n(I)$, we say that x is a linear combination of $\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m\} \subseteq V_n(I)$ if $x = (a_1 \times x_1) + (a_2 \times x_2) + \dots + (a_m \times x_m)$: $a_i \in K(I), x_i \in V_n(I)$.

Definition 2.8

Let $V_n(I)$ be a strong n-cyclic refined neutrosophic vector space over the n-cyclic refined neutrosophic field $K_n(I)$, x be an arbitrary element of $V_n(I)$, we say that x is a linear combination of $\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m\} \subseteq V_n(I)$ if $x = (a_1 \times x_1) + (a_2 \times x_2) + \dots + (a_m \times x_m)$: $a_i \in K_n(I), x_i \in V_n(I)$.

Definition 2.9

Let $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m\}$ be a subset of a weak n-cyclic refined neutrosophic vector space $V_n(I)$ over the field K , X is a weak linearly independent set if $\sum_{i=1}^m a_i \times x_i = \mathbf{0}$ implies $a_i = \mathbf{0}$; $a_i \in K$.

Definition 2.10

Let $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m\}$ be a subset of a strong n-cyclic refined neutrosophic vector space $V_n(I)$ over the n-cyclic refined neutrosophic field $K_n(I)$, X is a weak linearly independent set if $\sum_{i=1}^m a_i \times x_i = \mathbf{0}$ implies $a_i = \mathbf{0}$; $a_i \in K_n(I)$.

Definition 2.11

Let $V_n(I), W_n(I)$ be two strong n-cyclic refined neutrosophic vector space over the n-cyclic refined neutrosophic field $K_n(I)$, let $f: V_n(I) \rightarrow U_n(I)$ be a well defined map. It is called a strong n-cyclic refined neutrosophic homomorphism if:

$$f((a \times x) + (b \times y)) = a \times f(x) + b \times f(y) \text{ for all } x, y \in V_n(I), a, b \in K_n(I).$$

A weak n-cyclic refined neutrosophic homomorphism can be defined as the same.

Definition 2.12

Let $f: V_n(I) \rightarrow U_n(I)$ be a weak/strong n-cyclic refined neutrosophic homomorphism, we define:

$$(a) \text{ Ker}(f) = \{x \in V_n(I); f(x) = \mathbf{0}\}.$$

$$(b) \text{ Im}(f) = \{y \in U_n(I); \exists x \in V_n(I) \text{ and } y = f(x)\}.$$

Theorem 2.2

Let $f: V_n(I) \rightarrow U_n(I)$ be a weak n-cyclic refined neutrosophic homomorphism. Then

$$(a) \text{ Ker}(f) \text{ is a weak n-cyclic refined neutrosophic subspace of } V_n(I).$$

$$(b) \text{ Im}(f) \text{ is a weak nn-cyclic refined neutrosophic subspace of } U_n(I).$$

Proof:

(a) f is a vector space homomorphism since $V_n(I), U_n(I)$ are vector spaces, hence $\text{Ker}(f)$ is a subspace of the vector space $V_n(I)$, thus $\text{Ker}(f)$ is a weak n-cyclic refined neutrosophic subspace of $V_n(I)$.

(b) It hold by similar argument.

Theorem 2.3

Let $f: V_n(I) \rightarrow U_n(I)$ be a strong n-cyclic refined neutrosophic homomorphism. Then

(a) $Ker(f)$ is a strong n- cyclic refined neutrosophic subspace of $V_n(I)$.

(b) $Im(f)$ is a strong n- cyclic refined neutrosophic subspace of $U_n(I)$.

Proof:

(a) f is a module homomorphism since $V_n(I), U_n(I)$ are modules over the n-cyclic refined neutrosophic field $K_n(I)$, hence $Ker(f)$ is a submodule of the module $V_n(I)$, thus $Ker(f)$ is a strong n- cyclic refined neutrosophic subspace of $V_n(I)$.

(b) Holds by similar argument.

Definition 2.13 n-cyclic refined neutrosophic matrix

Let $A_{m \times n} = \{(\mathbf{a}_{ij}) : \mathbf{a}_{ij} \in K_n(I)\}$, where $K_n(I)$ is a n-cyclic refined neutrosophic field. We call to be the n-cyclic refined neutrosophic matrix.

Definition 2.14 n-cyclic refined neutrosophic square matrix

Let $A_{m \times n}$ is a neutrosophic matrix. We call to be the n-cyclic refined neutrosophic square matrix if $m = n$.

Example 2.1

Let $n = 3$, then

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 1 + I_1 + 2I_2 - I_3 & 2 - I_1 - 2I_3 & -1 + I_1 + I_2 + I_3 \\ I_2 + I_3 & 3 + I_1 + 2I_2 & I_1 + I_2 + I_3 \\ 1 - I_1 - I_3 & 4 - I_1 + I_2 - I_3 & -2 - I_1 + 3I_2 - I_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

A is a 3-cyclic refined neutrosophic square matrix.

A can be written as:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & -1 \\ 0 & 3 & 0 \\ 1 & 4 & -2 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 \end{pmatrix} I_1 + \begin{pmatrix} 2 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 2 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 3 \end{pmatrix} I_2 + \begin{pmatrix} -1 & -2 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 \end{pmatrix} I_3$$

Example 2.2

Let $n = 4$, then

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} -I_1 + I_2 - I_4 & 1 + I_1 - I_3 + I_4 & 1 + 2I_1 + I_2 + I_3 - I_4 \\ 3 - I_2 + 2I_3 - 3I_4 & -2 + I_1 + I_2 + I_4 & 2 - I_1 - I_2 + I_3 \\ 1 - I_1 - I_3 - 2I_4 & 5 + 3I_1 - I_2 - I_3 + 2I_4 & I_1 - 3I_2 - I_3 + I_4 \end{pmatrix}$$

A is a 4-cyclic refined neutrosophic square matrix.

A can be written as

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 3 & -2 & 2 \\ 1 & 4 & -2 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} -1 & -1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & -1 \\ -1 & 3 & 1 \end{pmatrix} I_1 + \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 1 & -1 \\ 0 & -1 & -3 \end{pmatrix} I_2 + \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 & 1 \\ 2 & 0 & 1 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 \end{pmatrix} I_3 + \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 1 & -1 \\ -3 & 1 & 0 \\ -2 & 2 & 1 \end{pmatrix} I_4$$

Example 2.3: Multiplication of n-cyclic refined neutrosophic square matrix

Let $A = A_0 + A_1I_1 + A_2I_2 + A_3I_3$, $B = B_0 + B_1I_1 + B_2I_2 + B_3I_3$ are two 3-cyclic refined neutrosophic square matrixes, where

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} -2 & 1 \\ 3 & 2 \end{pmatrix} I_1 + \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ -1 & -2 \end{pmatrix} I_2 + \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 2 \\ 3 & 0 \end{pmatrix} I_3, \quad B = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} -1 & -2 \\ 3 & 0 \end{pmatrix} I_1 + \begin{pmatrix} 4 & 2 \\ 3 & 0 \end{pmatrix} I_2 + \begin{pmatrix} 2 & -2 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} I_3$$

Then we have.

$$A \times B = A_0B_0 + A_0B_1I_1 + A_0B_2I_2 + A_0B_3I_3 + A_1B_0I_1 + A_1B_1I_1 + A_1B_2I_1I_2 + A_1B_3I_1I_3 + A_2B_0I_2 + A_2B_1I_2I_1 + A_2B_2I_2I_2 + A_2B_3I_2I_3 + A_3B_0I_3 + A_3B_1I_3I_1 + A_3B_2I_3I_2 + A_3B_3I_3I_3$$

$$A \times B = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} -1 & -2 \\ 3 & 0 \end{pmatrix} I_1 + \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 4 & 2 \\ 3 & 0 \end{pmatrix} I_2 + \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 2 & -2 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} I_3 + \begin{pmatrix} -2 & 1 \\ 3 & 2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} I_1 + \begin{pmatrix} -2 & 1 \\ 3 & 2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} -1 & -2 \\ 3 & 0 \end{pmatrix} I_1I_1 + \begin{pmatrix} -2 & 1 \\ 3 & 2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 4 & 2 \\ 3 & 0 \end{pmatrix} I_1I_2 + \begin{pmatrix} -2 & 1 \\ 3 & 2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 2 & -2 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} I_1I_3 + \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ -1 & -2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} I_2 + \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ -1 & -2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} -1 & -2 \\ 3 & 0 \end{pmatrix} I_2I_1 + \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ -1 & -2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 4 & 2 \\ 3 & 0 \end{pmatrix} I_2I_2 + \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ -1 & -2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 2 & -2 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} I_2I_3 + \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 2 \\ 3 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} I_3 + \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 2 \\ 3 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} -1 & -2 \\ 3 & 0 \end{pmatrix} I_3I_1 + \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 2 \\ 3 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 4 & 2 \\ 3 & 0 \end{pmatrix} I_3I_2 + \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 2 \\ 3 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 2 & -2 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} I_3I_3$$

Now, we have in 3-cyclic refined neutrosophic ring

$$I_1I_1 = I_1, I_2I_1 = I_1I_2 = I_3, I_1I_3 = I_3I_1 = I_1, I_2I_2 = I_1, I_2I_3 = I_3I_2 = I_2, I_3I_3 = I_3.$$

Thus.

$$A \times B = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 2 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} -1 & -2 \\ 2 & -2 \end{pmatrix} I_1 + \begin{pmatrix} 4 & 2 \\ 7 & 2 \end{pmatrix} I_2 + \begin{pmatrix} 2 & -2 \\ 3 & -1 \end{pmatrix} I_3 + \begin{pmatrix} -2 & -1 \\ 3 & 5 \end{pmatrix} I_1 + \begin{pmatrix} 5 & 4 \\ 3 & -6 \end{pmatrix} I_1 + \begin{pmatrix} 5 & -4 \\ 18 & 6 \end{pmatrix} I_3 + \begin{pmatrix} -3 & 5 \\ 8 & -4 \end{pmatrix} I_1 + \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 \\ -1 & -3 \end{pmatrix} I_2 + \begin{pmatrix} 2 & -2 \\ -5 & 2 \end{pmatrix} I_3 + \begin{pmatrix} 7 & 2 \\ -10 & -2 \end{pmatrix} I_1 + \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 \\ -4 & 0 \end{pmatrix} I_2 + \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 2 \\ 6 & -6 \end{pmatrix} I_3 + \begin{pmatrix} 6 & 0 \\ -3 & -6 \end{pmatrix} I_1 + \begin{pmatrix} 6 & 0 \\ 12 & 6 \end{pmatrix} I_2 + \begin{pmatrix} 2 & 2 \\ 6 & -6 \end{pmatrix} I_3$$

$$A \times B = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 2 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 12 & -1 \\ 3 & -15 \end{pmatrix} I_1 + \begin{pmatrix} 12 & 6 \\ 14 & 5 \end{pmatrix} I_2 + \begin{pmatrix} 11 & -4 \\ 28 & -5 \end{pmatrix} I_3$$

Example 2.4: Addition on n-cyclic refined neutrosophic rings

$$\text{Let } A = \begin{pmatrix} 2I_1 - I_2 + 3I_3 & 1 + I_1 + 2I_2 \\ -3 - 2I_1 + 4I_2 + I_3 & I_1 + I_3 \end{pmatrix}, \quad B = \begin{pmatrix} I_2 - 2I_3 & -2 + I_1 + I_2 + I_3 \\ 1 + I_1 - I_3 & 1 - I_1 - 4I_2 + I_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

Hence,

$$A + B = \begin{pmatrix} 2I_1 - I_2 + 3I_3 & 1 + I_1 + 2I_2 \\ -3 - 2I_1 + 4I_2 + I_3 & I_1 + I_3 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} I_2 - 2I_3 & -2 + I_1 + I_2 + I_3 \\ 1 + I_1 - I_3 & 1 - I_1 - 4I_2 + I_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$A + B = \begin{pmatrix} 2I_1 + 3I_3 & -1 + 2I_1 + 3I_2 + I_3 \\ -2 - I_1 + 4I_2 & 1 - 4I_2 + 2I_3 \end{pmatrix}.$$

5. Conclusions

In this paper, we have defined for the first time the concept of n -cyclic refined neutrosophic vector space, and n -cyclic refined neutrosophic real matrices. Also, we have presented some of their elementary properties and illustrated many examples to clarify the validity of our work.

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